

Reaction of C,N-Diphenylnitron with Vinylic Sulfones: Formation of Aryl Isoxazolidinyl Sulfones

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The formation of two new arylisoxazolidinylsulfones by the interaction of C,N-diphenylnitron with vinylic sulfones is described.

Although 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrones with 'activated' olefins, α , β -unsaturated esters, isocyanates, isothiocyanates and alkynes^{1a,b,c} ketene acetals^{1d} and unsaturated ketones^{1e} to form isoxazolidine is well established, there are no reports in the literature of reactions with vinylic sulfones. Accordingly, the utility of C,N-diphenylnitron as a coreactant with vinylic sulfones for the synthesis of isoxazolidinyl sulfones was investigated.

Treatment of C,N-diphenylnitron (I) with *cis*-phenyl- ω -styryl sulfone (IIa) and *cis*- ω -styryl *p*-tolyl sulfone (IIb) in refluxing benzene afforded respectively, 2,3,4-triphenyl-5-(phenylsulfonyl)isoxazolidine (IIIa) and 2,3,4-triphenyl-5-(*p*-tolylsulfonyl) isoxazolidine (IIIb) in good yields. A feasible reaction mechanism is given :

The ir and nmr spectral data are consistent with the structures, IIIa, b.

Further work on the nature of the stereochemistry of addition described herein is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL²

2,3,4-Triphenyl-5-(phenylsulfonyl)isoxazolidine (IIIa): A mixture of *cis*-phenyl- ω -styryl sulfone³ (2.32 g.; 0.01 mol.), C,N-diphenylnitron⁵ (1.97 g.; 0.01 mol.) in benzene

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- d. R. Scarpati, D. Sica and C. Santacroce (Univ. Naples), *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1966, **96**(4), 375; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, **65**, 8889.
- e. A. Lablache-combier and M. L. Villaume, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, **24**, 6951.
2. All the melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were run on a Beckman IRU spectrophotometer.
3. W. E. Truce and V. V. Badiger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 3277.

(25 ml.) was refluxed for about 40 hrs. The solution was concentrated to about half the volume and the addition of petroleum ether caused the precipitation of the crystals of 2,3,4-triphenyl-5-(phenylsulfonyl)isoxazolidine. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 2.9 g. (66%), m.p. 145–46°. (Found : C, 73.3; H, 5.5; N, 3.5. $C_{27}H_{23}O_3NS$ requires : C, 73.4; H, 5.2; N, 3.2 :). For compound IIIa ν (KBr) 8.63μ (SO_2); nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 5.42 (d, 3H), 4.3 (t, 4H), 5.59 (d, 5H), and 7.3 (m, aromatic protons).

The thin layer chromatography of this compound showed a single spot with benzene.

2,3,4-Triphenyl-5-(p-tolylsulfonyl)isoxazolidine (IIIb) : *cis*- ω -Styryl 1-*p*-tolylsulfone⁴, (2.46 g.; 0.01 mol.), C,N-diphenylnitrone⁵ (1.97 g.; 0.01 mol.) and 25 ml. benzene were taken and the reaction was carried out as in the previous case, when 2,3,4-triphenyl-5-(*p*-tolylsulfonyl)isoxazolidine was obtained as white solid which crystallised from ethanol. Yield 3.1 g. (68%), m.p. 156–57°. (Found : C, 73.47; H, 5.50; N, 3.45. $C_{28}H_{25}O_3NS$ requires : C, 73.84; H, 5.49; N, 3.08%). For compound IIIb ν (KBr) 8.7μ (SO_2); nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 5.25 (d, 3H), 4.3 (t, 4H), 5.63 (d, 5H), 7.3 (m, aromatic protons), and 2.3 (s, methyl protons).

The thin layer chromatography of this compound also showed a single spot with 50% benzene and 50% chloroform.

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